

The northern gene flow into southeastern East Asians inferred from genome-wide array genotyping

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ABSTRACT

The population history of Southeast China remains poorly understood due to the sparse sampling of present-day populations and far less modeling with ancient genomic data. We here newly reported genome-wide genotyping data from 207 present-day Han Chinese and Hmong-Mien-speaking She people from Fujian and Taiwan, southeast China. We co-analyzed with 66 early-Neolithic to Iron-Age ancient Fujian and Taiwan individuals obtained from literature to explore the genetic continuity and admixture based on the genetic variations of high-resolution time transect. We found the genetic differentiation between northern and southern East Asians defined by a north-south East Asian genetic cline and the studied southern East Asians were clustered in the southern end of this cline. We also found that southeastern coastal continental modern East Asians harbored the genetic differentiation with other southern Tai-Kadai, Hmong-Mien, Austronesian and Austroasiatic speakers, as well as geographically close Neolithic-to-Iron Age populations, but relatedly close to post-Neolithic Yellow River ancient, which suggested the influence of southward gene flow on the modern southern coastal gene pool. Besides, we also identified one new Hmong-Mien genetic cline in East Asia with the coastal Fujian She localizing at the intersection position between Hmong-Mien and Han clines in the principal component analysis. She people show stronger genetic affinity with southern East Asian indigenous populations with the main ancestry deriving from Hanben-related populations. The southeastern Han Chinese could be modeled with the primary ancestry deriving from the group related to the Yellow River Basin millet farmers and the remaining from groups related to southeastern ancient indigenous rice farmers, which was consistent with the northern China origin of modern southeastern Han Chinese and in line with the historically and archaeologically attested southward migrations of Han people and their ancestors. Interestingly, f_4 -statistics and three-way admixture model results showed both coastal ancient sources related to Austronesian speakers and inland ancient sources related to Austroasiatic speakers complexed the modern observed fine-scale genetic structure here. Our estimated north-south admixture time ranges based on the decay of the linkage disequilibrium spanned from the Bronze age to historic periods, suggesting the recent large-scale population migrations and subsequent admixture participated in the formation of modern Han in Southeast Asia.

KEYWORDS: population genomics, population transformation, genetic diversity, ancient DNA, genome-wide data

INTRODUCTION

Eastern Eurasia with larger geographical regions was enriched with plentiful cultural, linguistic, and genetic diversity. More than ten different language families/groups were widely existed here, including Uralic, Altai/trans-Eurasian (Turkic, Mongolic, Tungusic, Koreanic and Japonic) in Siberia and northern China; Sino-Tibetan, Austronesian, Austroasiatic, Hmong-Mien and Tai-Kadai in East Asia and Southeast Asia. Recent genetic studies based on the modern and/or ancient genomes of East Asians have subsequently elucidated the strong association between the

genetic structure, linguistic categories and geographical divisions, which were consistent with the proposed hypothesized of the language-farming co-dispersal model (He et al., 2020d; Ning et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020a; Yang et al., 2020; Zhang & Fu, 2020). Modern and ancient genetic studies based on the genetic variations of modern Sino-Tibetan and ancient Yellow River farmers have elucidated that the northern millet farmer expansion from northern China dispersed the Sino-Tibetan language (Wang et al., 2020a; Wang et al., 2020b), which was consistent with the common northern China origin of Sino-Tibetan languages based on the

84 linguistic phylogeny (Sagart et al., 2019; Zhang
85 et al., 2019). Similar studies based on the
86 ancient DNA from southern China and
87 Southeast Asia also found that the multiple
88 large-scale southward dispersals of southern
89 Chinese agriculturalists dissimilated the
90 Austroasiatic language via the first large-scale
91 population movements, and spread the
92 Austronesian via coastal migration routes, Tai-
93 Kadai, and Tibetan-Burman via the inland
94 routes (Lipson et al., 2018; McColl et al., 2018).
95 These gradually perfected language and genetic
96 landscape reconstructions were benefited from
97 the advances of ancient genome sequencing and
98 new algorithms of genome-wide data (Patterson
99 et al., 2012; Nielsen et al., 2017). Human
100 population formation processes in western
101 Eurasia have been fully explored and
102 reconstructed, including the population
103 substructure of Paleolithic Hunter-gatherers,
104 cultural and genetic transition from Hunter-
105 gathering to farming in the Neolithic revolution
106 and the expansion of steppe pastoralists and
107 their roles in the Indo-European language
108 dissimilation (Mathieson et al., 2018; Olalde
109 et al., 2018). However, the population
110 transformations of East Asians are retained in
111 its infancy stage. Thus, more genetic work
112 focused on

113 geographically/ethnically/spatiotemporally
114 populations was needed to explore the genetic
115 evolutionary history of East Asians.
116
117 China is of great interest in terms of deep
118 population history and ethnolinguistic/genetic
119 diversity, where is also the birthplace of pottery
120 and agriculture domesticated centers of
121 northern foxtail (*Setaria italica*) and
122 Broomcorn (*Panicum miliaceum*) millet and
123 Yangtze River rice (*Oryza sativa subsp.*
124 *japonica*). Population genetic studies based on
125 the low-density genetic markers, including
126 forensic-related short tandem repeats (STRs),
127 Insertion-Deletion (Indels), copy number
128 variations (CNV) and single nucleotide
129 polymorphisms (SNPs) in the autosome (Zou et
130 al., 2018; Chen et al., 2019; He et al., 2019c; He
131 et al., 2019a), X-chromosome (He et al., 2020a),
132 and Y-chromosome (He et al., 2019b), have
133 found that modern populations in China
134 featured extensive ethnolinguistic/genetic
135 diversity and significant genetic differentiation
136 among populations from different language
137 families. Spatiotemporally ancient DNA
138 analysis results have further deconstructed that
139 large-scale population movements and
140 accompanying admixture could promote the
141 formation of the increased genetic diversity and
142 decreased genetic differentiation (Harney et al.,
143 2018; Wang et al., 2020a). Our recent genome-

144 wide studies focused on populations from
145 lowland East Asia and highland Tibetan Plateau,
146 as well as northern and southern East Asians
147 also showed significant genetic differentiation
148 and complex demographic processes among
149 them (He et al., 2020b; He et al., 2020d; Wang
150 et al., 2020c), which also emphasized the
151 important role of modern geographically
152 isolated or marginalized people in the
153 demographic history reconstruction. Thus,
154 finer-scale population genetic structure
155 explorations from other peripheral regions of
156 East Asia were important for the understanding
157 of the gene pool and demographic history of
158 ancient and modern populations.
159

160 Han Chinese are the dominant population in
161 China and possess demographic importance for
162 molecular anthropology, population, and
163 forensic genetics. Wang et al. recently
164 reconstructed one of the most important
165 admixture models based on the ancient East
166 Asian genomes and found that modern Han
167 Chinese originated from the common ancestor
168 of Sinitic and Tibetan-Burman speakers in the
169 middle and upper Yellow River associated with
170 the millet farmers (Wang et al., 2020a). Yang et
171 al. also found that southward migrations of the
172 ancient northern East Asians played an
173 important role in the formation of the gene pool
174 of the southern East Asians (Yang et al., 2020).
175 Thus, comprehensive population genetic
176 surveys of ancient and modern southern East
177 Asians were important to elucidate the
178 population relationships of modern southern
179 East Asians and their northern and southern
180 possible ancestors. Until now, 66 early-
181 Neolithic to historic individuals from the Fujian
182 and Taiwan have been reported (Wang et al.,
183 2020a; Yang et al., 2020), which provided a
184 high-resolution time transect of the peripheral
185 region of southeast China to study the regional
186 specific population dynamics. Here, we
187 genotyped genome-wide data of over 700,000
188 SNPs in 207 unrelated individuals from 11
189 geographically/ethnically diverse populations
190 (Figure 1A) and combined all available modern
191 and ancient East Asians to reconstruct the
192 population history of southeastern Asian based
193 on the typical and advanced population genetic
194 methods (PCA, ADMIXTURE, Fst, TreeMix,
195 ALDER, *f*-statistics including *f*₃, *f*₄,
196 *qpAdm/qpWave*, *qpGraph*). We found a
197 complex population admixture history in
198 southeastern continental East Asia since the
199 Early Neolithic period, which is different from
200 the observed long-term genetic continuity in
201 other marginal regions of East Asia, such as the
202 Tibetan Plateau (Jeong et al., 2016) and Amur
203 River basin (Siska et al., 2017; Wang et al.,

204 2020a).

205 MATERIALS AND METHODS

206 **Ethical approval, Sample collection and**
207 **genotyping.** We obtained informed consent
208 from 207 individuals from 11 populations in
209 southeastern Asia and collected the saliva with
210 a saliva collection tube. Our study protocol has
211 been approved via the medical review board at
212 Xiamen University (Approval Number:
213 XDYX2019009). All procedures were
214 conducted also in accordance with the
215 recommendations stated in the Helsinki
216 Declaration of 2000 (Association, 2001).
217 Genomic DNA was extracted using the
218 PureLink Genomic DNA Mini Kit (Thermo
219 Fisher Scientific) and qualified via
220 Quantifiler™ Human DNA Quantification Kit
221 (Applied Biosystems, Foster City, CA, USA).
222 All samples were genotyped at the WeGene
223 company (Shenzhen). We used the default
224 parameters to conduct the genotype calling. We
225 finally used Plink 1.9 to filter the new
226 genotyped data and only remained the data with
227 the individual genotype site missing rate less
228 than 0.01 (mind: 0.01) and SNPs missing rate
229 less than 0.01 (geno: 0.01). We finally obtained
230 a dataset of 699,537 SNPs in 207 unrelated
231 individuals after further filtered data via HWE.

232
233
234 **Data preparation and two working datasets.**
235 We merged newly obtained genotype data with
236 previously published modern and ancient
237 genomic data and obtained two working
238 datasets of the Human-Origin-merged dataset
239 (72K dataset) and 1240K-merged dataset (193K
240 dataset). The 72K dataset comprised more
241 geographically/ethnically modern populations
242 genotyped via the Affymetrix Human-Origins
243 chip platform, which was suitable for
244 downstream descriptive analyses (PCA and
245 ADMIXTURE), and the 193K dataset with
246 higher-density SNPs suitable for following
247 quantitative analyses
248 ([https://reich.hms.harvard.edu/downloadable-](https://reich.hms.harvard.edu/downloadable-genotypes-present-day-and-ancient-dna-data-compiled-published-papers)
249 [genotypes-present-day-and-ancient-dna-data-](https://reich.hms.harvard.edu/downloadable-genotypes-present-day-and-ancient-dna-data-compiled-published-papers)
250 [compiled-published-papers](https://reich.hms.harvard.edu/downloadable-genotypes-present-day-and-ancient-dna-data-compiled-published-papers)). We also included
251 recently published ancient genome-wide data
252 from Nepal (Jeong et al., 2016), Mongolia
253 (Wang et al., 2020a), Siberia (Mathieson et al.,
254 2015; Sikora et al., 2019), China (Ning et al.,
255 2020; Wang et al., 2020a; Yang et al., 2020) and
256 Southeast Asia (Lipson et al., 2018; McColl et
257 al., 2018) in the population genomic analyses.

258 Global ancestry analysis

259 **Principal component analysis.** We carried out
260 the overall-East-Asian principal component
261 analysis (PCA) by merging the newly
262 genotyped Fujian and Taiwan individuals with

264 reference panels from both northern and
265 southern East Asians and southern-East-Asian
266 PCA focused on the Sinitic, Austronesian,
267 Austroasiatic, Hmong-Mien, Tai-Kadai
268 speakers and ancient southern East Asians using
269 the smartpca built-in EIGENSOFT packages
270 (Patterson et al., 2012). All included ancient
271 populations from Russia, Mongolia, Japan,
272 China and Nepal were projected onto the
273 modern backgrounds of the two-dimensional
274 plots.

275
276 **Model-based ADMIXTURE analysis.** We
277 first used Plink 1.9 (Purcell et al., 2007; Chang
278 et al., 2015) to prune (linkage disequilibrium
279 pruning) the successive variants with a squared
280 correlation greater than 0.4 in 200 SNPs and
281 sliding windows with 25 SNP in each step (--
282 indep-pairwise 200 25 0.4). The pruned dataset
283 consisted of new genotype data and previously
284 published modern and ancient non-Africans,
285 which was used to explore the East Asian
286 substructure. We ran ADMIXTURE 1.3.0
287 (Alexander et al., 2009) using unsupervised
288 mode and predefined ancestral populations
289 ranging from 2 to 20 (K: 2~20). We calculated
290 the cross-validation errors to choose the best-
291 fitted model.

292
293 **Pairwise Fst genetic distances.** We used Plink
294 1.9 (Purcell et al., 2007; Chang et al., 2015) and
295 our in-house script to calculate the pairwise Fst
296 indexes (Weir & Cockerham, 1984).

297
298 **F-statistics.** We calculated admixture- f_3 -
299 statistics in the form $f_3(\text{Source1}, \text{Source2};$
300 $\text{Fujian/Taiwan populations})$ using the $qp3pop$
301 program with default parameters in
302 ADMIXTOOLS (Patterson et al., 2012) to
303 explore the potential existing admixture signals
304 and calculated outgroup- $f_3(\text{Eurasian1};$
305 $\text{Eurasian2}; \text{Mbuti})$ to measure the shared
306 genetic drifts between the focused populations
307 and their reference groups. We also estimated
308 the f_4 -statistics values using the $qpDstat$
309 program and calculated the standard errors
310 using the default block jackknife (Patterson et
311 al., 2012).

312 Phylogenetic relationship reconstructions.

313 We first constructed the Neighbor-joining
314 phylogenetic tree via the TreeMix (Pickrell &
315 Pritchard, 2012) with the migration events
316 ranging from 2 to 20 to explore the relationship
317 between Fujian/Taiwan populations and their
318 neighboring modern and ancient reference
319 populations. And then we also constructed
320 another Neighbor-joining tree based on the
321 inverse outgroup- f_3 -based genetic distance
322 matrix.

324
325 **Multidimensional scaling analysis.** We carried
326 out multidimensional scaling analysis based on
327 the inverse outgroup- f_3 -based genetic distance
328 matrix using SPSS software and then visualized
329 in R software.

330
331 **Streams of ancestry and inference of mixture**
332 **proportions.** We used *qpWave* as implemented
333 in ADMIXTOOLS (Patterson et al., 2012) to
334 explore the minimum number of ancestral
335 sources needed to illuminate the observed
336 genetic variations in newly studied populations
337 and used *qpAdm* to quantify the ancestral
338 proportions of each ancestral populations. All
339 eleven newly-studied populations were used as
340 the left or tested populations and nine
341 worldwide populations (Mbuti,
342 Russia_Ust_Ishim, Russia_Kostenki14, Papuan,
343 Australian, Mixe, Russia_MA1_HG, Onge,
344 Atayal) were used as the right/reference
345 populations. The additional parameter of
346 'allsnps: YES' was used here.

347
348 **Admixture graph modeling.** We used
349 *qpGraph* (Patterson et al., 2012) to construct
350 two admixture graphs based on the one simple
351 seed skeletal framework and one complex
352 framework with two archaic introgression
353 events (Neanderthal introgression to non-
354 African and Denisovan introgression to
355 Australasian (Green et al., 2010; Reich et al.,
356 2010)). We finally fitted all studied eleven
357 populations on these two models to explore the
358 ancestral admixture proportions for their
359 northern and southern East Asian ancestral
360 proxies.

361
362 **Dating of gene-flow events.** We used multiple
363 Admixture-induced Linkage Disequilibrium for
364 Evolutionary Relationships (MALDER) to
365 estimate the admixture times with 31 potential
366 ancestral candidates (Loh et al., 2013). We used
367 29 years of the length of one generation and
368 calculated the years before the Common Era
369 (BCE): $Y=1950-29*(ALDER\text{-calculated years}-$
370 $1)$.

371
372 **Y-chromosomal and mtDNA haplogroup**
373 **assignment.** We used our in-house scripts and
374 the identified derived upstream alleles and
375 ancestral downstream alleles to assign to
376 haplogroups.

377 RESULTS

378 Population genetic structure of southeastern 379 modern and ancient East Asians

380 We reported approximately 700K genome-wide
381 SNPs in 207 Han Chinese and She individuals
382 from Fujian and Taiwan in southeastern China
383

384 and merged with 66 geographically close
385 ancient people, neighboring East Asians to
386 study the population dynamics of the
387 southeastern coast in East Asia. We first
388 conducted overall-East-Asian PCA based on the
389 72K dataset to assess the genetic affinity
390 between newly genotyped populations and
391 published ancient and present-day populations.
392 We found three genetic clines including
393 northern cline (Tungusic and Mongolic
394 speakers at one end and Tibeto-Burman
395 speakers at the other end), southern cline
396 (Austronesian and Austroasiatic speakers at one
397 end and Hmong-Mien at the other end) and the
398 intermediate Han Chinese cline between
399 Tibeto-Burman and Tai-Kadai people (**Figure**
400 **1B**). Fujian and Taiwan populations were
401 localized at the southmost end of the Han
402 Chinese cline and showed a close relationship
403 with modern Tai-Kadai-speaking populations
404 and ancient southern East Asians (Liangdao,
405 Hanben, Tanshishan, Xitoucun and so on).
406 Regional-southern-East-Asian PCA focused on
407 Han and southern East Asians showed a clear
408 finer-scale population substructure. Here, we
409 found four genetic sub-clines, including
410 Austronesian, Austroasiatic, Sinitic and
411 Hmong-Mien clines, which were consistent
412 with the linguistic affiliations. The Tai-Kadai-
413 speaking populations and ancient southern East
414 Asians were positioned in the middle of the
415 above four gradient groups (**Figure 1C**).
416 Interestingly, we identified one Hmong-Mien
417 genetic cline here which showed a close genetic
418 relationship with newly studied Han Chinese,
419 Hmong-Mien-speaking She and Tai-Kadai-
420 speaking populations.

421 To further explore the ancestry composition of
422 Fujian and Taiwan populations and their genetic
423 similarity with their geographically close
424 ancient populations, we carried out model-
425 based ADMIXTURE analysis among 4,130
426 non-African modern and ancient individuals
427 from 355 populations (mainly from eastern
428 Eurasia and also included representative
429 populations from Europe, Oceania and
430 America). We found obvious genetic
431 differences between modern and ancient
432 southeastern Asians but a relatively stronger
433 extent of genetic homogenization between
434 modern and ancient northern East Asians
435 although genetic differentiation could be
436 identified. When $K=10$, we observed three
437 ancestry components in newly studied
438 populations: Orange ancestry predominated in
439 southeastern modern Austronesian (Ami and
440 Atayal) and ancient groups (Hanben,
441 Tanshishan and Xitoucun), Yellow ancestry
442 enriched in Nepal ancients and modern Tibetans
443 and pink ancestry maximized in ancient Jomon

444 people. When K=11, a new bronze ancestry was
 445 maximized in Hmong-Mien-speaking Hmong,
 446 which was also enriched in Pathen and

447 dominant in our studied She and Han Chinese
 448 groups.

450 **Figure 1 Population genetic structure inferred from the descriptive methods.**

451 (A) Geographical positions of 11 newly studied populations from Fujian province in Southeastern China and positions of previously
 452 published ancient Southeastern coastal East Asians. (B-C) The principal component analysis focused on the genetic variations
 453 between 11 studied populations and all East Asians (B) or southern/modern and ancient East Asians (C). Ancient people from South
 454 Siberia, Mongolia, Nepal, China were projected onto the modern genetic background. All modern populations were categorized
 455 with their language family's belongings. (D) ADMIXTURE results showed the individual/population ancestral compositions
 456 among the modern and ancient Non-Africans.
 457

459 **Admixture signatures and shared genetic drifts**

460 The genetic affinity among southeastern East Asians was further confirmed via the smallest
 461 pairwise F_{st} genetic distances (Table S1) and the largest shared genetic drift within them
 462 (Table S2). Fujian and Taiwan populations had the smaller genetic distances with
 463 geographically close present-day and ancient populations (from Fujian Tanshishan and
 464 Xitoucun and Taiwan Hanben sites) and also with northern Sinitic speakers. Outgroup- f_3 -
 465 statistics also showed that Fujian and Taiwan populations shared the most genetic drift with
 466 all East Asian Sinitic speakers, southern Tai-Kadai and Austronesian speakers, and Late
 467 Neolithic to Iron Age southern East Asians (f_3 -values reached ~ 0.3 , Figure 2A~B). We
 468 followingly performed the multidimensional scaling analysis (MDS) among modern and
 469 ancient East Asians based on the inverse f_3 -based genetic distances ($1/f_3$) and found similar
 470 patterns of genetic clusters as in PCA and ADMIXTURE results. Ancient coastal southern
 471 East Asians from Fujian and Taiwan clustered together and localized close with Austronesian
 472 populations, while ancient coastal and inland northern East Asians grouped separately and
 473 showed close relationships with modern and ancient populations from Tibet Plateau and
 474 northern China. Han Chinese and She populations in Fujian and Taiwan clustered

475 Neolithic to Iron Age southern East Asians (f_3 -values reached ~ 0.3 , Figure 2A~B). We
 476 followingly performed the multidimensional scaling analysis (MDS) among modern and
 477 ancient East Asians based on the inverse f_3 -based genetic distances ($1/f_3$) and found similar
 478 patterns of genetic clusters as in PCA and ADMIXTURE results. Ancient coastal southern
 479 East Asians from Fujian and Taiwan clustered together and localized close with Austronesian
 480 populations, while ancient coastal and inland northern East Asians grouped separately and
 481 showed close relationships with modern and ancient populations from Tibet Plateau and
 482 northern China. Han Chinese and She populations in Fujian and Taiwan clustered

491 tightly together between northern and southern
 492 East Asians or between northern Sinitic and
 493 southern Tai-Kadai speaking populations on a
 494 finer-scale (**Figure 2C**). We performed
 495 admixture- f_3 (*Source1, source2; eleven*
 496 *Fujian/Taiwan populations*) to explore the
 497 potential ancestral sources among 354 modern
 498 and ancient Eurasians with statistically
 499 significant f_3 -values with Z-scores less than -3.
 500 For Hmong-Mien-speaking She, we observed

501 the mixed signatures in 311 out of 66410
 502 ancestral candidates' pairs with one source
 503 usually from modern or ancient southern East
 504 Asians and the other from northern Tibetan-
 505 Burman/Tungusic/Mongolic-related
 506 populations (**Figure 2D-G**), such as the most
 507 negative f_3 value was f_3 (*Ami, Chamdo Tibetan;*
 508 *Fujian She*) = -6.423*SE.

511 f_3 (*Northern sources, Ami/Atayal/Hainan Li/Kankanaey/Taiwan Hanben; She_Fujian*)
 512 **Figure 2. Shared genetic drifts and mixture signals were revealed via outgroup- f_3 -statistics and admixture- f_3 -statistics.**
 513 (A-B) Heatmap of f_3 -statistic values showed the genetic affinity between Fujian She (A) or Fuzhou Han (B) and other Eurasian
 514 modern reference populations.
 515 (C) Multidimensional scaling analysis based on the matrix of the inverse shared genetic distance ($1/\text{outgroup-}f_3$) showed the genetic
 516 relationship between 11 Fujian populations and other modern and ancient East Asians.
 517 (D-G) Statistically significant admixture- f_3 -statistic signatures focused on Fujian She when we used the southern East Asians of
 518 Ami, Atayal, Li, Kankanaey and ancient Taiwan Hanben as the plausible southern sources.
 519

521 **Figure 3. Four-population-based statistics showed the asymmetrical genetic affinity between Fujian populations and their**
 522 **corresponding references.**
 523 (A) Symmetrical- f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Studied Fujian population 1, Studied Fujian population 2; modern and ancient Eurasian}$
 524 $\text{reference populations, Mbuti})$.
 525 (B) Affinity- f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Reference population1, Reference population2; Fujian She, Mbuti})$ shared the stronger
 526 genetic affinity between Fujian She and modern and ancient southern East Asians.
 527 (C) Asymmetrical f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Reference populations, Fujian She; Ancestral sources or Reference populations, Mbuti})$
 528 showed the genetic continuity and admixture between modern Fujian populations and their ancient predecessors.
 529
 530

531 **Genetic continuity and admixture**

532 Qualitative analysis of PCA and ADMIXTURE
 533 model-based clustering showed the genetic
 534 differentiation between northern and southern
 535 East Asians defined by a north-south cline and

536 intermediate positions of our newly reported
 537 Han Chinese and She populations in the north-
 538 south cline. Qualitative testing based on the
 539 admixture- f_3 and outgroup- f_3 -statistics further
 540 showed the closer genetic affinity of our newly

541 reported populations with southern East Asians
 542 and Bronze to Iron Age northern East Asians.
 543 To examine genetic continuity and potential
 544 admixture events between southeastern coastal
 545 Han Chinese and She with ancient East Asians,
 546 we performed five different types of f_4 -statistics.
 547 Firstly, we conducted $f_4(\text{Han}/\text{She1}; \text{Han}/\text{She2};$
 548 $\text{Eurasians}, \text{Mbuti})$ and found no population

549 substructure among 10 Han Chinese
 550 populations (Table S3). However, we detected
 551 more allele sharing between southern
 552 indigenous populations (Dong Kankanaey) or
 553 northern coastal Neolithic Xiaojingshan
 554 samples with She people compared with Han
 555 Chinese (Figure 3A).

557 **Figure 4. Pairwise $qpWave$ p-values for each pair of populations.** Values greater than 0.05 are marked with two parallel plus
 558 (++) signs and greater than 0.01 are marked with one plus sign.
 559

560
 561 Secondly, to further explore the genetic
 562 heterogeneity among Sino-Tibetan speakers,
 563 Chinese ancient populations and southern
 564 Chinese and Southeast Asians from four
 565 language families and validate the genetic
 566 homogeneity among the newly-studied
 567 southeastern Chinese populations, we
 568 performed pairwise $qpWave$ -based analysis
 569 among 113 populations used in regional-PCA
 570 analysis based on the powerful set of outgroups
 571 (Mbuti, Ust_Ishim, Kostenki14, Papuan,
 572 Australian, Mixe, MA1, Onge,

573 Mongolia_N_East, Wuqi_EN, Bianbian_EN,
 574 Liangdao2_EN, Jomon, Yumin_EN,
 575 Chokhopani and Yamnaya). The $qpWave$
 576 analysis was conducted via various sets of f_4 -
 577 statistics in the form $f_4(\text{left}_1, \text{left}_i; \text{right}_1, \text{right}_i)$
 578 to explore the gene flow events from the used right
 579 populations to the left populations (Patterson et
 580 al., 2012). We found genetic differences
 581 between linguistically different populations and
 582 genetic differentiation between modern
 583 southeastern East Asians and their
 584 geographically close predecessors (Table S4),

585 but confirmed the genomic similarity within the
 586 linguistically/geographically close populations,
 587 especially in our studied populations (**Figure 4**).
 588 Here, we could identify pairwise p_{rank0} larger than
 589 0.05, which suggested the genetic cladality
 590 existed between two used left populations
 591 compared with the used right outgroups. We
 592 could identify five clade clusters, including four
 593 homogeneous clusters (northern homogeneous
 594 group, southern homogeneous group, northern
 595 ancient homogeneous group and southern
 596 Hmong-Mien/Tai-Kadai homogenous group).
 597 All studied Fujian and Taiwan populations
 598 showed similar homogeneous signals of genetic
 599 cladality with each other, as well as with
 600 previously reported Fujian Han, Bijie
 601 Chuanqing, Miao and She included in the
 602 Human Genome Diversity Project. Interestingly,
 603 homogeneous signals between the newly-

604 studied populations and ancient northern
 605 populations (Jinchankou, Dacaozi, Pingliangtai,
 606 Wadian, Haojiatai and Xiaowu) from the
 607 Central plain, where is the birthplace of Chinese
 608 Civilization, suggesting the southward gene
 609 flow events and their significant impact on the
 610 gene pool composition of modern southeastern
 611 coastal populations. Here, we also observed
 612 genetic heterogeneity between modern
 613 southeastern Han populations and
 614 geographically close Neolithic predecessors,
 615 inland modern Tai-Kadai/Hmong-Mien
 616 speakers, as well as with northern inland ancient
 617 populations from the upper Yellow River,
 618 suggested their differentiated demographic
 619 admixture history.
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622 **Figure 5. qp-Adm/qp-Wave results showed the detailed ancestral composition in the best-fitted two-way admixture model.**
 623 Here, we used Iron Age Taiwan Hanben as the southern ancestral sources which possessed a stronger affinity with modern
 624 Austronesian and Tai-Kadai-speaking populations. Early Neolithic to Iron Age northern East Asian from the Yellow River Basin
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and their surrounding regions were used as the possible northern Sources. New studied populations and their corresponding p_{rank1} in the $qpWave$ tests were listed in the left part of the bar plots. White error bar denoted as the standard error.

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Figure 6. Genetic models fitted using qpGraph showed the formation of modern Southern East Asian Fujian populations. We fitted the two admixture graphs by sequentially adding populations to the seed models, and finally fitted all new studied populations in simple seed graph model (A~B) and complex seed graph model (C~D).

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Thirdly, to further explore the genetic affinity formally or additional gene-flow events from surrounding heterogeneous ancestral source candidates among the 193K dataset, we performed $f_4(Eastern Eurasians1, Eastern Eurasians2; 11 studied populations, Mbuti)$ and found similar patterns of shared ancestry among Han/She and their reference populations (Table S5). No significant negative f_4 -statistic values

were observed in $f_4(Eastern Eurasians1, Eastern Eurasians2; Fujian She, Mbuti)$ when southern East Asians (modern Ami, Han, She, Tujia, Miao and Atayal and ancient Hanben and Gongguan) and northern middle Neolithic to Iron Age (Luoheguxiang_LBIA, Jiaozuoniecun_LBIA, Haojiatai_LN, Erdaojingzi_LN and Xiaowu_MN) used as the first reference populations (Eastern Eurasians1,

653 the right populations listed in **Figure 3B**,
 654 which suggested significant more allele sharing
 655 of Fujian She with them than with other
 656 reference populations (Eastern Eurasians2, the
 657 bottom populations listed in **Figure 3B**).
 658 Compared with Neolithic people from Siberia
 659 and Inner Mongolia and Early Neolithic
 660 Liangdao people in southeast China, Fujian She
 661 possessed excess sharing alleles with Late

662 Neolithic to modern East Asians. In detail,
 663 significant positive values in $f_4(\text{Northern Yellow}$
 664 $\text{River ancient Yangshao/Houli populations,}$
 665 $\text{other reference populations; southeastern}$
 666 $\text{Han/She, Mbuti})$ observed here implied the
 667 southward dispersal of gene flow from the
 668 Yellow River into the southeast coast since the
 669 Late Neolithic (**Figure 3B**).

671 **Figure 7. Phylogenetic relationships between eleven Fujian populations and other modern and ancient East Asian reference**
 672 **populations based on the shared f_3 -based genetic distance matrix ($1/f_3$).** All included modern populations were grouped with
 673 their linguistic affiliations.
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676 Fourth, we used $f_4(\text{reference population 1,}$
 677 $\text{southeastern Han/She; reference population 2,}$
 678 $\text{Mbuti})$ to evaluate whether modern
 679 southeastern East Asians were consistent with
 680 directly descending from ancient populations
 681 from Yellow River Basin or southeastern
 682 coastal regions (here we used as reference
 683 population 2, bottom populations listed in
 684 **Figure 3C**). We identified the most negative f_4 -
 685 values when we used modern southern groups
 686 (Kinh, Lahu, Thai, Han, Miao, She, Tujia, Ami,

687 Dai, Atayal) and ancient Iron Age Hanben
 688 samples as the reference population 2 (**Table**
 689 **S6**). We also observed the consistent genetic
 690 affinity of negative f_4 -values when northern
 691 modern (Tu, Naxi and Yi) and ancient
 692 populations (Dacaozi_IA, Pingliangtai_LN,
 693 Haojiatai_LN and Jiaozuonicun_LBIA) and
 694 southern ancient coastal populations
 695 (Chuanyun_H, Liangdao1_EN, Qihe_EN and
 696 Taiwan_Gongguan, Tanshishan_LN,
 697 Liangdao2_EN and Xitoucun_LN) as the

698 reference population 2 (Figure 3C). These
 699 observed negative signals showed their affinity
 700 with southeastern East Asians, consistent with
 701 the assumptions that reference population 2 was

702 predefined as their ancient ancestral source
 703 candidates.
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Figure 8. The estimated admixture times for Fujian populations based on the decay rates of admixture-induced linkage disequilibrium. All listed two-way admixture models were well-fitted models with the expected p values and Z-scores. The marked admixture years were calculated as: $Y=1950-29*(\text{calculated used generations}-1)$.

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Fifth, to further explore whether one or more ancestral populations (mainly focused on geographically close southeastern coastal ancient East Asians, and homogeneous ancient populations from the Yellow River basin) could be fitted as the unique ancestral populations for our studied modern populations, we performed $f_4(\text{candidate source}, 11 \text{ studied populations}; \text{reference populations}, Mbuti)$. We used the

721 population that can give a negative f_4 -value as
 722 “reference population 2” in the above f_4
 723 statistics as the candidate source (Table S6).
 724 Genetic cladality between Southeastern East
 725 Asians and Wuzhuangguoliang, Suogang and
 726 Chuanyun ancient populations were observed,
 727 which may be used as direct evidence for
 728 studied populations directly descended from
 729 these three populations or related populations.

730 Here, it should be cautious that all identified
731 ancestral sources may be biased by the low-
732 overlapping SNPs and high contamination of
733 these samples (Wang et al., 2020a; Yang et al.,
734 2020). In fact, we observed additional
735 admixture signals via symmetrical f_4 -statistics.
736 The populations from northern and southern
737 East Asia (bottom population lists in **Figure 3C**)
738 shared excess alleles with our studied Fujian
739 populations compared to the candidate source
740 populations (reference populations listed in the
741 right list in **Figure 3C**). Consistent with the
742 negative admixture signals observed in
743 admixture- f_3 -statistics in the form $f_3(\text{candidate}$
744 *source, reference populations; 11 studied*
745 *populations)*, we concluded that southeastern
746 modern Han and She cannot be modeled as
747 descending directly from geographically close
748 Neolithic to historic ancient populations
749 without additional admixture related to ancient
750 Yellow River Basin agriculturalists. Modern
751 southeastern East Asian was formed via
752 complex admixed processes.

753
754 Summarily, several lines of evidence supported
755 the southward gene flow from northern East
756 Asia into the southeastern continental East Asia
757 region, which is also confirmed via f_4 -statistics
758 based on the merged Human Origin dataset
759 (**Tables S7–8**). First, a recent ancient genomic
760 study conducted via Yang et al. demonstrated
761 that southward migrations from the Yellow
762 River basin significantly influenced the gene
763 pool of Fujian Late Neolithic populations (Yang
764 et al., 2020). As they observed that the Late
765 Neolithic Tanshishan and Xitoucun people
766 harbored more Yellow farmer-related ancestry
767 compared with early Liangdao people (Yang et
768 al., 2020), suggested by the observed negative
769 values in $f_4(\text{Liangdao,}$
770 *Tanshishan_LN/Xitoucun_LN; Yellow River*
771 *millet farmer; Mbuti)*. Second, combined
772 analysis among ancient genomes reported via
773 Yang et al. (Yang et al., 2020), Ning et al. (Ning
774 et al., 2020) and Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2020a)
775 also revealed the continuous southward from
776 Yellow River millet further into Taiwan Iron
777 Age Hanben and Gongguan populations in the
778 southeastern continental East Asia marginal
779 region, as the negative f_4 -values in
780 $f_4(\text{Liangdao_EN/Tanshishan_LN/Xitoucun_LN,}$
781 *Hanben_Taiwan/Gongguan_Taiwan; ancient*
782 *northern East Asian, Mbuti)*. Third, Further
783 evidence from f_4 -statistics (**Figure 3**)
784 demonstrated that present-day southeastern
785 East Asians harbored more northern East Asian
786 related ancestry compared to their early
787 ancestor as evidenced via the f_4 -statistics in the
788 form $f_4(\text{ancient southeastern continental East}$
789 *Asians, modern Fujian/Taiwan populations;*

790 *ancient northern East Asians, Mbuti)*. Thus,
791 millet agricultural development and millet
792 farmer southward expansion continued to have
793 an impact on the formation of the gene pool of
794 the southern East Asians. These north-south
795 admixture processes were further confirmed via
796 the *qpWave/qpAdm, qpGraph* and MALDER
797 results in the next section.

798 **Admixture processes and their potential** 799 **phylogenetic relationship**

800 Results from the descriptive and qualitative
801 analyses suggested genetic variations or allele
802 frequency of studied southeastern populations
803 tended to be at an intermediate position between
804 northern and southern East Asians. Thus, we
805 further used *qpWave* analysis to study the
806 minimum ancestral populations that could be
807 used to explain our observed genetic pattern and
808 found that two ancestral candidates can be best-
809 fitted ($p_{\text{rank1}} > 0.05$) with one powerful set of
810 outgroups. We employed *qpWave* and *qpGraph*
811 to estimate the ancestral proportion of their
812 potential ancestral sources. First, we used all
813 available northern millet farmer-related
814 populations as the northern sources and Iron
815 Age Hanben from Taiwan as the southern
816 sources and used the *qpAdm* to estimate the
817 mixing proportions. We observed She and
818 southeastern Han derived more northern
819 ancestry from the ancient Yellow River farming
820 populations in the majority of the models except
821 for the Yumin_EN-Hanben model (**Figure 5**).
822 Second, we well-fitted two *qpGraph*-based
823 phylogenies and added all eleven studied
824 populations on the skeletal frameworks. We
825 found all included populations could be fitted as
826 admixtures between groups related to the
827 Yellow River millet farmers and Yangtze River
828 ghost populations (**Figure 6**). Third, we have
829 found the genetic differences between southern
830 coastal East Asians and southern inland East
831 Asians. Thus, to further explore the gene flow
832 influence from inland southern East Asians
833 related to Austroasiatic speakers or their
834 ancestors on the genetic structure of modern
835 coastal populations, we conducted three-way
836 admixture models, in which twenty-one ancient
837 northern East Asians were used as the northern
838 sources, three ancient populations from
839 mainland Southeast Asia were used as inland
840 southern inland source and Ami from Taiwan as
841 the coastal source. We could successfully model
842 eleven studied populations as the admixture
843 results of major ancestry from northern China,
844 approximately equal ancestry from two
845 southern sources (**Table S9**).

846
847 Furthermore, Neighbor-joining phylogenetic
848 relationships constructed based on the matrix of
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1/ f_3 also found a tight cluster of southeastern coastal modern Han and She, which localized between northern meta-groups (Tungusic/Mongolic clade, ancient northern East Asian clade, ancient and modern Tibetan-Burman clade and northern Sinitic clade) and southern-meta groups (Hmong-Mien clade, southern Tibeto-Burman clade, Austronesian/ancient southern coastal East Asian clade, and Austroasiatic/Tai-Kadai clade). Here, we also found historic Chuanyun people clustered with Xiamen Han and Fujian Han, suggesting their more shared ancestral history (Figure 7). Similar patterns of phylogenetic relationships were evidenced by F_{st} genetic distance matrix. ALDER-based admixture times with different ancestral populations further showed the north-south population interaction and admixture occurred at least from Neolithic time and large-scale population contact occurred in the Bronze Age to the historic time (Figure 8).

Uniparental genetic structure of southeastern Asians

We assigned 207 mitochondrial genomes into 118 different terminal haplogroups with the corresponding frequency ranging from 0.0048 (1) to 0.0386 (F1a1, 8). Haplogroups F1a1, D4a, M7c1c, B4a, F1a and M8a were the dominant maternal lineages in southeastern East Asians (Table S10). We assigned 108 Y-chromosome genomes into 66 terminal haplogroups with the haplogroup frequency ranging from 0.0093 (1) to 0.0463 (O2a2b1a1a5a2, 5). O1a was regarded as the common founding lineage of modern southern Han, Tai-Kadai and Austronesian speaking populations, which comprised 0.2315 (25/108) of studied Han and She populations. Han-dominant O2a was the major lineage consisting of 0.4722 (51/108) of studied populations. It was interesting to find that one western Eurasian specific R1a1a1b2a2b1b and one Siberian-dominant Q1a1a1a1a~ were observed in southeastern Han Chinese, suggesting the long-range of mobility and admixture in eastern Eurasia.

DISCUSSION

Population genetic studies focused on East Asians have illustrated the geographically isolated populations or populations from the peripheral regions have a relatively homogenized structure with long-term genetic continuity. He et al. studied the genetic structure of the Tai-Kadai-speaking Li population from Hainan island using genome-wide data and found that the Li people were uniquely homogeneous with no obvious recent gene flow from mainland China (He et al., 2020b). Results

of genome-wide studies focused on highland-adaptive populations in the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau also found the primary ancestry of modern Tibetans derived from the millet agriculturalists from the middle and upper Yellow River Basin in northern China (Wang et al., 2020a). This work also demonstrated that modern core Tibetans and ancient Nepal people (Samdzong, Chokhopani, and Mebrak) acquired little additional gene flow when the human population permanently occupied the highland at least from late Neolithic time (approximately 3600 years ago) (Jeong et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2020a). Genetic evidence from Tungusic speakers residing in the peripheral region of Northeast Asia and geographically close ancient DevilsCave people also illuminated their long-term genetic stability at least from 7700 years ago (Siska et al., 2017). However, populations from other regions that may act as the homeland or corridors of population movement have complex demographical changes (Chen et al., 2019; He et al., 2020d). Here we comprehensively investigated the population genetic structure and admixture history in Fujian and Taiwan at the southeastern edge of East Asia. Our genetic analysis focusing on the genetic history from early Neolithic to modern populations demonstrated the past of the southeast coast was dynamic with multiple population mixing, for example, the gene flow from northern farming populations into the southeast coast. Generally, the population history of southern East Asia was complexed via the mixing process of different gene pools observed in this study, including southward dispersal northern East Asian gene pool, indigenous southern differentiated gene pools associated with the Austronesian, Hmong-Mien, Tai-Kadai and Austronesian speakers. Our quantitative analyses of ADMIXTURE and PCA consistently demonstrated that modern southern East Asians were differentiated into inland and coastal lineages, and studied southern continental East Asians harbored gene flow from a northern lineage related to the shared lineage of all Sino-Tibetan speakers and two southern indigenous lineages. Quantitative analyses via f -statistics, pairwise $qpWave$ and $qpAdm$ further confirmed the population migrations related to these three lineages that participated in the formation of southeastern coastal modern population genetic legacy. We also identified genetic differentiation between modern southeastern continental populations, and neighboring Neolithic populations and modern Austronesian speakers suggested that the southward gene flow events shifted the ancient genetic structure, which is consistent

970 with the geographical feature of the corridor in
971 ancient coastal population migrations and the
972 main starting point of the southward dispersal
973 of Austronesian speakers and their language
974 (Yang et al., 2020).

975
976 The origin of the Sino-Tibetan people remains
977 heavily debated due to three different
978 hypotheses been evidenced via linguistic,
979 historic findings to some extent, including the
980 North Indian origin hypothesis, Southwest
981 China/Tibetan-Yi Corridor hypothesis, and
982 northern China origin hypothesis. Our results
983 also supported the primary ancestry of modern
984 southeastern coastal Han Chinese originated
985 from northern China, which is consistent with
986 previous genome-wide analysis from
987 southernmost, Central and northern modern
988 Han Chinese (He et al., 2020c; He et al., 2020b;
989 He et al., 2020d). Linguistic evidence has also
990 illuminated the common origination of Sinitic
991 and Tibeto-Burman languages (Sagart et al.,
992 2019; Zhang et al., 2019) from north China, in
993 accordance with the archeologically
994 documented Yangshao/Majiyao-related
995 culture dispersal. Our results from the *qpAdm*
996 results have found the main ancestry of
997 southeastern Han deriving from northern millet
998 farmer related populations, which were further
999 confirmed via the *qpGraph*-based demographic
1000 models. Further, we identified the finer-scale
1001 population substructure among southern East
1002 Asians consistent with the linguistic affiliation,
1003 but differentiated with the observed genetic
1004 structure of southeastern coastal populations.
1005 Except for the previous identified Austronesian
1006 and Austroasiatic mainly from the Island and
1007 Mainland of Southeast Asia, here, we identified
1008 one new Hmong-Mien-speaking population
1009 genetic cline consisting of Hmong, Pathen and
1010 Dao from the mainland of southeastern Asia
1011 (Liu et al., 2020), Gejia, Dongjia, Xijia (Sun
1012 et al., 2020), Miao and She from southern China.
1013 Stronger southern East Asian affinity of Fujian
1014 She and its close relationship with populations
1015 from inland Hmong-Mien-speaking population
1016 genetic cline, consistent with the linguistic
1017 classification of She people. Here, we note we
1018 should pay greater attention to the limitation of
1019 sampling bias of Hmong-Mien She, which
1020 should be further confirmed with more ancient
1021 DNA from southern China and denser sampling
1022 of modern Hmong-Mien-speaking populations.

1023 CONCLUSION

1024 Genome-wide evidence from modern and
1025 ancient southeastern coastal East Asians
1026 demonstrated the continuous southward gene
1027 flow since the early Holocene has shaped their
1028 genetic landscape. Present-day southeastern

1030 Han and Hmong-Mien She derived ancestry
1031 from at least two ancient populations
1032 respectively associated with Yellow River
1033 millet farmers and Yangtze River rice
1034 agriculturalists. The obtained primary ancestry
1035 and the reconstructed phylogeny have provided
1036 genome-wide evidence of northern China origin
1037 of southeastern Han Chinese and ALDER-
1038 based admixture times further illuminated the
1039 large-scale southward migrations that occurred
1040 during Bronze Age and historic times. Finer-
1041 scale population substructure within southern
1042 East Asians visualized here could provide
1043 significant clues for further deep populations
1044 history reconstruction, rethink the language-
1045 farming-co-dispersal hypothesis and even
1046 present some genetic reference for experimental
1047 design of cohort studies related to precision
1048 medicine. More ancient DNA studies and
1049 denser modern population sampling should be
1050 further conducted to explore more details of the
1051 demographic developments of modern southern
1052 East Asians.

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1064 DATA AVAILABILITY

1065 Following the regulations and informed consent
1066 of this project and the regulations of the Human
1067 Genetic Resources Administration of China
1068 (HGRAC), the obtained raw data can be shared
1069 via personal communication with
1070 corresponding authors. We make the data
1071 available upon request by asking the person
1072 requesting the data to agree in writing to the
1073 following restrictions: 1, the data can be only
1074 used for studying population history; 2, the data
1075 cannot be used for commercial purposes; 3, the
1076 data cannot be used to identify the sample
1077 donors; 4, the data cannot be used for studying
1078 natural/cultural selections, medical or other
1079 related studies.

1080 DISCLOSURE OF POTENTIAL 1081 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

1082 The author declares no conflict of interest.

1083 REFERENCE

1084 Alexander DH, Novembre J, Lange K. 2009. Fast model-
1085 based estimation of ancestry in unrelated individuals.
1086 *Genome Res* 19: 1655-1664.

- 1091 Association WM. 2001. World medical association
1092 declaration of helsinki. Ethical principles for medical
1093 research involving human subjects. *Bulletin of the World
1094 Health Organization* 79: 373.
- 1095 Chang CC, Chow CC, Tellier LC, Vattikuti S, Purcell SM,
1096 Lee JJ. 2015. Second-generation plink: Rising to the
1097 challenge of larger and richer datasets. *Gigascience* 4: 7.
- 1098 Chen P, Wu J, Luo L, Gao H, Wang M, Zou X, Li Y, Chen
1099 G, Luo H, Yu L, Han Y, Jia F, He G. 2019. Population
1100 genetic analysis of modern and ancient DNA variations
1101 yields new insights into the formation, genetic structure,
1102 and phylogenetic relationship of northern han chinese.
1103 *Front Genet* 10: 1045.
- 1104 Green RE, Krause J, Briggs AW, Maricic T, Stenzel U,
1105 Kircher M, Patterson N, Li H, Zhai W, Fritz MH, Hansen
1106 NF, Durand EY, Malaspina AS, Jensen JD, Marques-Bonet
1107 T, Alkan C, Prufer K, Meyer M, Burbano HA, Good JM,
1108 Schultz R, Aximu-Petri A, Butthof A, Hober B, Hoffner B,
1109 Siegemund M, Weihmann A, Nusbaum C, Lander ES, Russ
1110 C, Novod N, Affourtit J, Egholm M, Verna C, Rudan P,
1111 Brajkovic D, Kucan Z, Gusic I, Doronichev VB,
1112 Golovanova LV, Lalueza-Fox C, de la Rasilla M, Fortea J,
1113 Rosas A, Schmitz RW, Johnson PLF, Eichler EE, Falush D,
1114 Birney E, Mullikin JC, Slatkin M, Nielsen R, Kelso J,
1115 Lachmann M, Reich D, Paabo S. 2010. A draft sequence of
1116 the neandertal genome. *Science* 328: 710-722.
- 1117 Harney E, May H, Shalem D, Rohland N, Mallick S,
1118 Lazaridis I, Sarig R, Stewardson K, Nordenfelt S, Patterson
1119 N, Hershkovitz I, Reich D. 2018. Ancient DNA from
1120 chalcolithic israel reveals the role of population mixture in
1121 cultural transformation. *Nat Commun* 9: 3336.
- 1122 He G, Zou X, Wang M, Liu J, Wang F, Hou Y, Wang Z.
1123 2020a. Population genetics, diversity, forensic
1124 characteristics of four chinese populations inferred from x-
1125 chromosomal short tandem repeats. *Leg Med (Tokyo)* 43:
1126 101677.
- 1127 He G, Wang Z, Zou X, Wang M, Liu J, Wang S, Ye Z, Chen
1128 P, Hou Y. 2019a. Tai-kadai-speaking gelao population:
1129 Forensic features, genetic diversity and population structure.
1130 *Forensic Sci Int Genet* 40: e231-e239.
- 1131 He G, Wang Z, Su Y, Zou X, Wang M, Chen X, Gao B, Liu
1132 J, Wang S, Hou Y. 2019b. Genetic structure and forensic
1133 characteristics of tibeto-burman-speaking u-tsang and kham
1134 tibetan highlanders revealed by 27 y-chromosomal str. *Sci
1135 Rep* 9: 7739.
- 1136 He G, Ren Z, Guo J, Zhang F, Zou X, Zhang H, Wang Q, Ji
1137 J, Yang M, Zhang Z, Zhang J, Nabijiang Y, Huang J, Wang
1138 CC. 2019c. Population genetics, diversity and forensic
1139 characteristics of tai-kadai-speaking bouyei revealed by
1140 insertion/deletions markers. *Mol Genet Genomics* 294:
1141 1343-1357.
- 1142 He G, Wang Z, Guo J, Wang M, Zou X, Tang R, Liu J,
1143 Zhang H, Li Y, Hu R, Wei LH, Chen G, Wang CC, Hou Y.
1144 2020b. Inferring the population history of tai-kadai-
1145 speaking people and southernmost han chinese on hainan
1146 island by genome-wide array genotyping. *Eur J Hum Genet*
1147 28: 1111-1123.
- 1148 He G, Wang M, Li Y, Zou X, Yeh HY, Tang R, Yang X,
1149 Wang Z, Guo J, Luo T, Zhao J, Sun J, Hu R, Wei LH, Chen
1150 G, Hou Y, Wang CC. 2020c. Fine-scale north-to-south
1151 genetic admixture profile in shaanxi han chinese revealed
1152 by genome-wide demographic history reconstruction.
1153 *Journal of Systematics and Evolution*: 0-.
- 1154 He GL, Li YX, Wang MG, Zou X, Yeh HY, Yang XM, Wang
1155 Z, Tang RK, Zhu SM, Guo JX, Luo T, Zhao J, Sun J, Xia
1156 ZY, Fan HL, Hu R, Wei LH, Chen G, Hou YP, Wang CC.
1157 2020d. Fine-scale genetic structure of tujia and central han
1158 chinese revealing massive genetic admixture under
1159 language borrowing. *Journal of Systematics and Evolution*
1160 n/a.
- 1161 Jeong C, Ozga AT, Witonsky DB, Malmstrom H, Edlund H,
1162 Hofman CA, Hagan RW, Jakobsson M, Lewis CM,
1163 Aldenderfer MS, Di Rienzo A, Warinner C. 2016. Long-
1164 term genetic stability and a high-altitude east asian origin
1165 for the peoples of the high valleys of the himalayan arc.
1166 *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 113: 7485-7490.
- 1167 Lipson M, Cheronet O, Mallick S, Rohland N, Oxenham M,
1168 Pietrusewsky M, Pryce TO, Willis A, Matsumura H,
1169 Buckley H, Domett K, Nguyen GH, Trinh HH, Kyaw AA,
1170 Win TT, Pradier B, Broomandkoshbacht N, Candilio F,
1171 Changmai P, Fernandes D, Ferry M, Gamarra B, Harney E,
1172 Kampuansai J, Kutanan W, Michel M, Novak M,
1173 Oppenheimer J, Sirak K, Stewardson K, Zhang Z,
1174 Flegontov P, Pinhasi R, Reich D. 2018. Ancient genomes
1175 document multiple waves of migration in southeast asian
1176 prehistory. *Science* 361: 92-95.
- 1177 Liu D, Duong NT, Ton ND, Van Phong N, Pakendorf B, Van
1178 Hai N, Stoneking M. 2020. Extensive ethnolinguistic
1179 diversity in vietnam reflects multiple sources of genetic
1180 diversity. *Mol Biol Evol* 37: 2503-2519.
- 1181 Loh PR, Lipson M, Patterson N, Moorjani P, Pickrell JK,
1182 Reich D, Berger B. 2013. Inferring admixture histories of
1183 human populations using linkage disequilibrium. *Genetics*
1184 193: 1233-1254.
- 1185 Mathieson I, Lazaridis I, Rohland N, Mallick S, Patterson
1186 N, Roodenberg SA, Harney E, Stewardson K, Fernandes D,
1187 Novak M, Sirak K, Gamba C, Jones ER, Llamas B,
1188 Dryomov S, Pickrell J, Arsuaga JL, de Castro JM, Carbonell
1189 E, Gerritsen F, Khokhlov A, Kuznetsov P, Lozano M, Meller
1190 H, Mochalov O, Moiseyev V, Guerra MA, Roodenberg J,
1191 Verges JM, Krause J, Cooper A, Alt KW, Brown D, Anthony
1192 D, Lalueza-Fox C, Haak W, Pinhasi R, Reich D. 2015.
1193 Genome-wide patterns of selection in 230 ancient eurasi-
1194 ans. *Nature* 528: 499-503.
- 1195 Mathieson I, Alpaslan-Roodenberg S, Posth C, Szecsenyi-
1196 Nagy A, Rohland N, Mallick S, Olalde I,
1197 Broomandkoshbacht N, Candilio F, Cheronet O,
1198 Fernandes D, Ferry M, Gamarra B, Fortes GG, Haak W,
1199 Harney E, Jones E, Keating D, Krause-Kyora B,
1200 Kucukkalipci I, Michel M, Mittnik A, Nagele K, Novak M,
1201 Oppenheimer J, Patterson N, Pfrengle S, Sirak K,
1202 Stewardson K, Vai S, Alexandrov S, Alt KW, Andreescu R,
1203 Antonovic D, Ash A, Atanassova N, Bacvarov K, Gusz-
1204 MB, Bocherens H, Bolus M, Boroneant A, Boyadzhiev Y,
1205 Budnik A, Burmaz J, Chohadzhiev S, Conard NJ, Cottiaux
1206 R, Cuka M, Cupillard C, Drucker DG, Elenski N, Francken
1207 M, Galabova B, Ganetsovski G, Gely B, Hajdu T,
1208 Handzhyiska V, Harvati K, Higham T, Iliev S, Jankovic I,
1209 Karavanic I, Kennett DJ, Komso D, Kozak A, Labuda D,
1210 Lari M, Lazar C, Leppke M, Leshtakov K, Vetro DL, Los D,
1211 Lozanov I, Malina M, Martini F, McSweeney K, Meller H,
1212 Mendusic M, Mirea P, Moiseyev V, Petrova V, Price TD,
1213 Simalcik A, Sineo L, Slaus M, Slavchev V, Stanev P,
1214 Starovic A, Szeniczey T, Talamo S, Teschler-Nicola M,
1215 Thevenet C, Valchev I, Valentin I, Vasilyev S, Veljanovska
1216 F, Venelinova S, Veselovskaya E, Viola B, Virag C,
1217 Zaninovic J, Zauner S, Stockhammer PW, Catalano G,
1218 Krauss R, Caramelli D, Zarina G, Gaydarska B, Lillie M,
1219 Nikitin AG, Potekhina I, Papathanasiou A, Boric D, Bonsall
1220 C, Krause J, Pinhasi R, Reich D. 2018. The genomic history
1221 of southeastern europe. *Nature* 555: 197-203.
- 1222 McColl H, Racimo F, Vinner L, Demeter F, Gakuhari T,
1223 Moreno-Mayar JV, van Driem G, Gram Wilken U, Seguin-
1224 Orlando A, de la Fuente Castro C, Wasef S, Shoocongdej R,
1225 Souksavatdy V, Sayavongkhamdy T, Saidin MM, Allentoft
1226 ME, Sato T, Malaspina AS, Aghakhanian FA, Komeliusen
1227 P, Prohaska A, Margaryan A, de Barros Damgaard P,
1228 Kaewsutthi S, Lertrit P, Nguyen TMH, Hung HC, Minh
1229 Tran T, Nghia Truong H, Nguyen GH, Shahidan S,
1230 Wiradnyana K, Matsumae H, Shigehara N, Yoneda M,
1231 Ishida H, Masuyama T, Yamada Y, Tajima A, Shibata H,
1232 Toyoda A, Hanihara T, Nakagome S, Deviese T, Bacon AM,
1233 Durringer P, Ponche JL, Shackelford L, Patole-Edoumba E,
1234 Nguyen AT, Bellina-Pryce B, Galipaud JC, Kinaston R,
1235 Buckley H, Pottier C, Rasmussen S, Higham T, Foley RA,
1236 Lahr MM, Orlando L, Sikora M, Phipps ME, Oota H,
1237 Higham C, Lambert DM, Willerslev E. 2018. The
1238 prehistoric peopling of southeast asia. *Science* 361: 88-92.
- 1239 Nielsen R, Akey JM, Jakobsson M, Pritchard JK, Tishkoff
1240 S, Willerslev E. 2017. Tracing the peopling of the world

- 1241 through genomics. *Nature* 541: 302-310.
- 1242 Ning C, Li T, Wang K, Zhang F, Li T, Wu X, Gao S, Zhang
- 1243 Q, Zhang H, Hudson MJ, Dong G, Wu S, Fang Y, Liu C,
- 1244 Feng C, Li W, Han T, Li R, Wei J, Zhu Y, Zhou Y, Wang CC,
- 1245 Fan S, Xiong Z, Sun Z, Ye M, Sun L, Wu X, Liang F, Cao
- 1246 Y, Wei X, Zhu H, Zhou H, Krause J, Robbeets M, Jeong C,
- 1247 Cui Y. 2020. Ancient genomes from northern China suggest
- 1248 links between subsistence changes and human migration.
- 1249 *Nat Commun* 11: 2700.
- 1250 Olalde I, Brace S, Allentoft ME, Armit I, Kristiansen K,
- 1251 Booth T, Rohland N, Mallick S, Szecsenyi-Nagy A, Mittnik
- 1252 A, Altena E, Lipson M, Lazaridis I, Harper TK, Patterson N,
- 1253 Broomandkoshbacht N, Diekmann Y, Faltyskova Z,
- 1254 Fernandes D, Ferry M, Hamey E, de Knijff P, Michel M,
- 1255 Oppenheimer J, Stewardson K, Barclay A, Alt KW, Liesau
- 1256 C, Rios P, Blasco C, Miguel JV, Garcia RM, Fernandez AA,
- 1257 Banffy E, Bernabo-Brea M, Billoin D, Bonsall C, Bonsall
- 1258 L, Allen T, Buster L, Carver S, Navarro LC, Craig OE, Cook
- 1259 GT, Cunliffe B, Denaire A, Dinwiddie KE, Dodwell N,
- 1260 Ernee M, Evans C, Kucharik M, Farre JF, Fowler C,
- 1261 Gassenbeek M, Pena RG, Haber-Uniarte M, Haduch E, Hey
- 1262 G, Jowett N, Knowles T, Massy K, Pfrengle S, Lefranc P,
- 1263 Lemercier O, Lefebvre A, Martinez CH, Olmo VG,
- 1264 Ramirez AB, Maurandi JL, Majo T, McKinley JI,
- 1265 McSweeney K, Mende BG, Modi A, Kulcsar G, Kiss V,
- 1266 Czene A, Patay R, Endrodi A, Kohler K, Hajdu T, Szeniczey
- 1267 T, Dani J, Bernert Z, Hoole M, Cheronet O, Keating D,
- 1268 Veleminsky P, Dobes M, Candilio F, Brown F, Fernandez
- 1269 RF, Herrero-Corral AM, Tusa S, Carnieri E, Lentini L,
- 1270 Valenti A, Zanini A, Waddington C, Delibes G, Guerra-
- 1271 Doce E, Neil B, Brittain M, Luke M, Mortimer R, Desideri
- 1272 J, Besse M, Brucken G, Furmanek M, Haluszko A,
- 1273 Mackiewicz M, Rapinski A, Leach S, Soriano I, Lillios KT,
- 1274 Cardoso JL, Pearson MP, Wlodarczyk P, Price TD, Prieto P,
- 1275 Rey PJ, Risch R, Rojo Guerra MA, Schmitt A, Serralongue
- 1276 J, Silva AM, Smrcka V, Vergnaud L, Zilhao J, Caramelli D,
- 1277 Higham T, Thomas MG, Kennett DJ, Fokkens H, Heyd V,
- 1278 Sheridan A, Sjogren KG, Stockhammer PW, Krause J,
- 1279 Pinhasi R, Haak W, Bames I, Lalueza-Fox C, Reich D. 2018.
- 1280 The beaker phenomenon and the genomic transformation of
- 1281 northwest Europe. *Nature* 555: 190-196.
- 1282 Patterson N, Moorjani P, Luo Y, Mallick S, Rohland N,
- 1283 Zhan Y, Genschorek T, Webster T, Reich D. 2012. Ancient
- 1284 admixture in human history. *Genetics* 192: 1065-1093.
- 1285 Pickrell JK, Pritchard JK. 2012. Inference of population
- 1286 splits and mixtures from genome-wide allele frequency data.
- 1287 *PLoS Genet* 8: e1002967.
- 1288 Purcell S, Neale B, Todd-Brown K, Thomas L, Ferreira MA,
- 1289 Bender D, Maller J, Sklar P, de Bakker PI, Daly MJ, Sham
- 1290 PC. 2007. PLINK: A tool set for whole-genome association
- 1291 and population-based linkage analyses. *Am J Hum Genet* 81:
- 1292 559-575.
- 1293 Reich D, Green RE, Kircher M, Krause J, Patterson N,
- 1294 Durand EY, Viola B, Briggs AW, Stenzel U, Johnson PL,
- 1295 Maricic T, Good JM, Marques-Bonet T, Alkan C, Fu Q,
- 1296 Mallick S, Li H, Meyer M, Eichler EE, Stoneking M,
- 1297 Richards M, Talamo S, Shunkov MV, Derevianko AP,
- 1298 Hublin JJ, Kelso J, Slatkin M, Paabo S. 2010. Genetic
- 1299 history of an archaic hominin group from Denisova cave in
- 1300 Siberia. *Nature* 468: 1053-1060.
- 1301 Sagart L, Jacques G, Lai Y, Ryder RJ, Thouzeau V,
- 1302 Greenhill SJ, List JM. 2019. Dated language phylogenies
- 1303 shed light on the ancestry of Sino-Tibetan. *Proc Natl Acad*
- 1304 *Sci USA* 116: 10317-10322.
- 1305 Sikora M, Pitulko VV, Sousa VC, Allentoft ME, Vinner L,
- 1306 Rasmussen S, Margaryan A, de Barros Damgaard P, de la
- 1307 Fuente C, Renaud G, Yang MA, Fu Q, Dupanloup I,
- 1308 Giampoudakis K, Nogueira-Bravo D, Rahbek C, Kroonen G,
- 1309 Peyrot M, McColl H, Vasilyev SV, Veselovskaya E,
- 1310 Gerasimova M, Pavlova EY, Chasnyk VG, Nikolskiy PA,
- 1311 Gromov AV, Khartanovich VI, Moiseyev V, Grebenyuk PS,
- 1312 Fedorchenko AY, Lebedintsev AI, Slobodin SB,
- 1313 Malyarchuk BA, Martiniano R, Meldgaard M, Arppe L,
- 1314 Palo JU, Sundell T, Mannermaa K, Putkonen M,
- 1315 Alexandersen V, Prineas C, Baimukhanov N, Malhi RS,
- 1316 Sjogren KG, Kristiansen K, Wessman A, Sajantila A, Lahr
- 1317 MM, Durbin R, Nielsen R, Meltzer DJ, Excoffier L,
- 1318 Willerslev E. 2019. The population history of northeastern
- 1319 Siberia since the Pleistocene. *Nature* 570: 182-188.
- 1320 Siska V, Jones ER, Jeon S, Bhak Y, Kim HM, Cho YS, Kim
- 1321 H, Lee K, Veselovskaya E, Balueva T, Gallego-Llorente M,
- 1322 Hofreiter M, Bradley DG, Eriksson A, Pinhasi R, Bhak J,
- 1323 Manica A. 2017. Genome-wide data from two early
- 1324 Neolithic East Asian individuals dating to 7700 years ago. *Sci*
- 1325 *Adv* 3: e1601877.
- 1326 Sun J, Zhao J, Cheng H-Z, Yang X, He G, Guo J, Li Y, Hu
- 1327 R, Chen G, Wei L-H, Wang C-C. 2020. Genetic affinity and
- 1328 substructure of Hmong-Mien speaking populations inferred
- 1329 from genome-wide array genotyping of three unrecognized
- 1330 ethnic groups Dongjia, Xijia and Gejia. *Mol Genet Genomics*.
- 1331 Wang C-C, Yeh H-Y, Popov AN, Zhang H-Q, Matsumura H,
- 1332 Sirak K, Cheronet O, Kovalev A, Rohland N, Kim AM,
- 1333 Bernardos R, Tumen D, Zhao J, Liu Y-C, Liu J-Y, Mah M,
- 1334 Mallick S, Wang K, Zhang Z, Adamski N,
- 1335 Broomandkoshbacht N, Callan K, Culleton BJ, Eccles L,
- 1336 Lawson AM, Michel M, Oppenheimer J, Stewardson K,
- 1337 Wen S, Yan S, Zalzal F, Chuang R, Huang C-J, Shiung C-
- 1338 C, Nikitin YG, Tabarev AV, Tishkin AA, Lin S, Sun Z-Y,
- 1339 Wu X-M, Yang T-L, Hu X, Chen L, Du H, Bayarsaikhan J,
- 1340 Mijiddorj E, Erdenebaatar D, Iderkhantai T-O, Myagmar E,
- 1341 Kanzawa-Kiriyama H, Nishino M, Shinoda K-i, Shubina
- 1342 OA, Guo J, Deng Q, Kang L, Li D, Li D, Lin R, Cai W,
- 1343 Shrestha R, Wang L-X, Wei L, Xie G, Yao H, Zhang M, He
- 1344 G, Yang X, Hu R, Robbeets M, Schiffels S, Kennett DJ, Jin
- 1345 L, Li H, Krause J, Pinhasi R, Reich D. 2020a. The genomic
- 1346 formation of human populations in East Asia. *bioRxiv*:
- 1347 2020.2003.2025.004606.
- 1348 Wang M, Zou X, Ye H-Y, Wang Z, Liu Y, Liu J, Wang F,
- 1349 Yao H, Chen P, Tao R, Wang S, Wei L-H, Tang R, Wang C-
- 1350 C, He G. 2020b. Peopling of Tibet Plateau and multiple
- 1351 waves of admixture of Tibetans inferred from both modern
- 1352 and ancient genome-wide data. *bioRxiv*.
- 1353 Wang M, Zou X, Ye H-Y, Wang Z, Liu Y, Liu J, Wang F,
- 1354 Yao H, Chen P, Tao R, Wang S, Wei L-H, Tang R, Wang C-
- 1355 C, He G. 2020c. Peopling of Tibet Plateau and multiple
- 1356 waves of admixture of Tibetans inferred from both modern
- 1357 and ancient genome-wide data. *bioRxiv*:
- 1358 2020.2007.2003.185884.
- 1359 Weir BS, Cockerham CC. 1984. Estimating *F*-statistics for
- 1360 the analysis of population structure. *Evolution* 38: 1358-
- 1361 1370.
- 1362 Yang MA, Fan X, Sun B, Chen C, Lang J, Ko YC, Tsang
- 1363 CH, Chiu H, Wang T, Bao Q, Wu X, Hajdinjak M, Ko AM,
- 1364 Ding M, Cao P, Yang R, Liu F, Nickel B, Dai Q, Feng X,
- 1365 Zhang L, Sun C, Ning C, Zeng W, Zhao Y, Zhang M, Gao
- 1366 X, Cui Y, Reich D, Stoneking M, Fu Q. 2020. Ancient DNA
- 1367 indicates human population shifts and admixture in northern
- 1368 and southern China. *Science* 369: 282-288.
- 1369 Zhang M, Fu Q. 2020. Human evolutionary history in
- 1370 eastern Eurasia using insights from ancient DNA. *Curr Opin*
- 1371 *Genet Dev* 62: 78-84.
- 1372 Zhang M, Yan S, Pan W, Jin L. 2019. Phylogenetic evidence
- 1373 for Sino-Tibetan origin in northern China in the late Neolithic.
- 1374 *Nature* 569: 112-115.
- 1375 Zou X, Wang Z, He G, Wang M, Su Y, Liu J, Chen P, Wang
- 1376 S, Gao B, Li Z, Hou Y. 2018. Population genetic diversity
- 1377 and phylogenetic characteristics for high-altitude adaptive
- 1378 Kham Tibetan revealed by dnatypr(tm) 19 amplification
- 1379 system. *Front Genet* 9: 630.
- 1380
- 1381 **Legends of Figures**
- 1382 **Figure 1 Population genetic structure inferred from the**
- 1383 **descriptive methods.**
- 1384 (A) Geographical positions of 11 newly studied populations
- 1385 from Fujian province in Southeastern China and positions
- 1386 of previously published ancient Southeastern coastal East
- 1387 Asians.
- 1388 (B-C) Principal component analysis focused on the genetic
- 1389 variations between 11 studied populations and all East
- 1390 Asians (B) or southern modern and ancient East Asians (C).

1391 Ancient people from South Siberia, Mongolia, Nepal, China
1392 were projected onto the modern genetic background. All
1393 modern populations were categorized with their language
1394 family's belongings.

1395 **(D)** ADMIXTURE results showed the
1396 individual/population ancestral compositions among the
1397 modern and ancient Non-Africans.

1398 **Figure 2. Shared genetic drifts and mixture signals
1399 revealed via outgroup- f_3 -statistics and admixture- f_3 -
1400 statistics.**

1401 **(A~B)** Heatmap of f_3 -statistic values showed the genetic
1402 affinity between Fujian She **(A)** or Fuzhou Han **(B)** and
1403 other Eurasian modern reference populations.

1404 **(C)** Multidimensional scaling analysis based on the matrix
1405 of the inverse shared genetic distance ($1/\text{outgroup-}f_3$)
1406 showed the genetic relationship between 11 Fujian
1407 populations and other modern and ancient East Asians.

1408 **(D~G)** Statistically significant admixture- f_3 -statistic
1409 signatures focused on Fujian She when we used the
1410 southern East Asians of Ami, Atayal, Li, Kankanaey and
1411 ancient Taiwan Hanben as the plausible southern sources.

1412 **Figure 3. Four-population-based statistics showed the
1413 asymmetrical genetic affinity between Fujian
1414 populations and their corresponding references.**

1415 **(A)** Symmetrical- f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Studied Fujian
1416 population1, Studied Fujian population2; modern and
1417 ancient Eurasian reference populations, Mbuti})$.

1418 **(B)** Affinity- f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Reference
1419 population1, Reference population2; Fujian She, Mbuti})$
1420 shared the stronger genetic affinity between Fujian She and
1421 modern and ancient southern East Asians.

1422 **(C)** Asymmetrical f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Reference
1423 populations, Fujian She; Ancestral sources or Reference
1424 populations, Mbuti})$ showed the genetic continuity and
1425 admixture between modern Fujian populations and their
1426 ancient predecessors.

1427 **Figure 4. Pairwise p-values of qpWave for each pair of
1428 populations.** Values greater than 0.05 are marked with two
1429 parallel plus (++) signs and greater than 0.01 are marked
1430 with one plus sign.

1431 **Figure 5. qpAdm/qpWave results showed the detailed
1432 ancestral composition in the best-fitted two-way
1433 admixture model.** Here, we used Iron Age Taiwan Hanben
1434 as the southern ancestral sources which possessed a stronger
1435 affinity with modern Austronesian and Tai-Kadai-speaking
1436 populations. Early Neolithic to Iron Age northern East
1437 Asian from the Yellow River Basin and their surrounding
1438 regions were used as the possible northern Sources. New
1439 studied populations and their corresponding p_rank1 in the
1440 qpWave tests were listed in the left part of the bar plots.
1441 White err bar denoted as the standard error.

1442 **Figure 6. Genetic models fitted using qpGraph showed
1443 the formation of modern Southern East Asian Fujian
1444 populations.** We fitted the two admixture graphs by
1445 sequentially adding populations to the seed models, and
1446 finally fitted all new studied populations in simple seed
1447 graph model **(A~B)** and complex seed graph model **(C~D)**.

1448 **Figure 7. Phylogenetic relationships between eleven
1449 Fujian populations and other modern and ancient East
1450 Asian reference populations based on the shared f_3 -
1451 based genetic distance matrix ($1/f_3$).** All included modern
1452 populations were grouped with their linguistic affiliations.

1453 **Figure 8. The estimated admixture times for Fujian
1454 populations based on the decay rates of admixture-
1455 induced linkage disequilibrium.** All listed two-way
1456 admixture models were well-fitted models with the
1457 expected p values and Z-scores. The marked admixture
1458 years were calculated as: $Y=1950-29^*(\text{calculated used
1459 generations}-1)$.

1460

1461 **Legends of supplementary Tables**

1462 **Table S1.** The pairwise Fst genetic distance among 49 East
1463 Asian modern and ancient populations.

1464 **Table S2.** The shared genetic drift between eleven
1465 southeastern continental Han/She populations and other

1466 ancient/modern Eurasians.

1467 **Table S3.** Differentiated shared alleles among eleven
1468 studied populations compared to modern and ancient
1469 Eurasians estimated via symmetrical f_4 -statistics in the
1470 form $f_4(\text{Han/She1, Han/She2; eleven studied populations,
1471 Mbuti})$ based on the merged Human Origin dataset.

1472 **Table S4.** Pairwise p_rank0 values in qpWave analysis
1473 among 113 East Asian modern and ancient populations.

1474 **Table S5.** Symmetrical f_4 -statistics in the form
1475 $f_4(\text{Reference population1, reference population2; eleven
1476 studied populations, Mbuti})$ to test their genetic affinity
1477 between Eurasian reference populations based on the
1478 merged 1240K dataset.

1479 **Table S6.** Affinity- f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Reference
1480 population1, eleven studied populations; reference
1481 population2, Mbuti})$ to explore the genetic continuity and
1482 admixture between potential ancestral sources and
1483 Fujian/Taiwan populations based on the merged 1240K
1484 dataset.

1485 **Table S7.** Symmetrical f_4 -statistics in the form
1486 $f_4(\text{Reference population1, reference population2; eleven
1487 studied populations, Mbuti})$ to test their genetic affinity
1488 between Eurasian reference populations based on the
1489 merged Human Origin dataset.

1490 **Table S8.** Affinity- f_4 -statistics in the form $f_4(\text{Reference
1491 population1, eleven studied populations; reference
1492 population2, Mbuti})$ to explore the genetic continuity and
1493 admixture between potential ancestral sources and
1494 Fujian/Taiwan populations based on the merged Human
1495 Origin dataset.

1496 **Table S9.** qpAdm-based ancestral admixture proportion in
1497 eleven studied populations via three-way admixture models.

1498 **Table S10.** Haplogroup distribution in eleven studied
1499 populations.

